

SLACK VS. GITTER

TABLE 1: Comparison of Slack and Gitter

	Gitter	
Type and pricing	Proprietary and freemium (free for the basic features)	Open source and free
Intended audiences	Built for corporations, expanded to open communities.	Built for open communities, expanded to corporations.
Joining	Can only join by requesting or receiving an invite from a team.	Logging in with existing Twitter or GitHub account.
Identity	A different identity for every joined team.	Single identity - Uses Twitter or GitHub username and avatar.
Open communities	To read discussions in open communities on Slack, an invitation is required.	All rooms on Gitter have addresses like: https://gitter.im/nodejs/node that anyone can access and read. Joining a room allows you to post.
Major integrations	Google Drive, Trello, Dropbox, Box, Heroku, IBM Bluemix, Crashlytics, GitHub, Runscope, Zendesk and Zapier	GitHub, Trello, Jenkins, Travis CI, Drone, Heroku, and Bitbucket